

PHILOSOPHICAL VIEWS OF M.K.MAMARDASHVILI

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7932220>

Kosbergenova Nurzada Tolibaevna

Student of Karakalpak State University named after Berdak

Abstract.

M.K.Mamardashvili's relationship between existence and man, his understanding of philosophy and the creation of existence by man. About the emergence of loneliness and their importance in existence. It is about the birth of philosophical thoughts at a single moment and their lifetime in moments.

Methods.

The systematic-structural approach based on objectivity, universality, concreteness, logical, and historical dialectical principles was used in the research. This makes it possible to see the concepts and information as a whole system of human society.

Introduction.

Philosophy is a science that studies the general laws of the human world system. It forms a subjective and objective world view. These aspects are one of the important and main tasks of philosophy. The ratio of existence to thinking, consciousness to matter, which has become a central issue in the history of philosophy since ancient times, and the issue of man became relevant in Mamardashvili's philosophy.

Results And Discussion

A person faces not only problems related to life, production and others. What is the world we live in? does chaos prevail on earth?", "Can a person know the world?", "What is knowledge?", "What is the meaning of human life?", "What is the purpose and value of life?" tries to answer general and deep level questions⁵². Mamardashvili's philosophical direction was to search for the a priori condition of human existence. It was more to study its development and self-formation. In his commentary on philosophy, he stated that philosophy is a means of studying the relationship between the world and man, its development and formation.

According to Mamardashvili, philosophy was not about imparting knowledge about the world, but it was necessary to establish contact with the world and study

⁵² A.K.Berdimurayova- Filofofiya o'qish qo'llanmasi. (Nukus 2010)

human existence.⁵³ (Also in his philosophical theory, thoughts like these are not worldly problems, what is the substance at the center of the world? How did the world appear, it is directly related to man. In Mamardashvili, we meet a new view of human existence, consciousness, and therefore the emergence of singularities together Being is manifested in a different way. Mamardashvili, moving his own and others' consciousness, deeply approaching it, creates vivid thoughts, new ideas and gives meaning to existence. For Mamardashvili, philosophy and culture are the thinking of a person, even each idea is a source for the birth of a new life, a new being. There is no essence in the empirical world, there is an infinity without essence, the essence is in being, in finite ideas, the whole drama of human life is primarily in ideas appears and only then appears in the empirical world.⁵⁴ This is where we can see singles popping up. If the thinking of a person is based on the emergence of a new existence, the concept of existence may be different.

Mamardashvili answers such questions as follows: my philosophy is not the whole doctrine of the ideal foundations of existence, but its specific form. In this case, the objective approach to the world has created its own subjectivity - he wants to say that existence is seen differently.

Mamardashvili created existence from consciousness, that is, from ideas. He must have thought that it is necessary to start knowing the world from man, because he created existence from thinking (consciousness), which is the main issue of philosophy. Maybe that's why it is assumed that his philosophical direction started with the issue of man (reciprocity of mind and existence). The special appearance of existence is also seen here. He created the existence from the mind-idea and demonstrated it in one aspect in the glorification of man. Mamardashvili's philosophical views were influenced by the teachings of Socrates, Descartes (I think, therefore I am) and a number of other philosophers. Now let's talk about the issue of consciousness and existence: the world is infinite, ideas are also infinite. Ontology divides the world into two parts. 1) The existence of the world and 2) the existence of things in the world. Based on this theory, we can divide the infinite world and the limited world or knowledge. All the knowledge we have can help us to know the existence of things in the world, but it is not enough to know the existence of the world. That is, based on Mamardashvili's philosophy, the existence of things in the world can be considered equal to the world of ideas created by the human mind. Human knowledge is limited, but the world is infinite. We create our own world of ideas from the knowledge we have learned about the existence of

⁵³ М.К.Мамардашвили- Эстетика мышления. (М.2008)

⁵⁴ К.К.Чикобава- Идеи антропоидеи в философии М.К. Мамардашвили (Грузия 2004)

that world. Using the limit of our knowledge as a means of knowing the world, we increase our understanding of the existence of things in the world, and in this context, if we talk about singularities here: I think it is related to consciousness (thinking, perception). should be. The reason is that everyone has an opinion about the world based on his level of thinking, knowledge, and understanding (the world is created by sub-activity). In the matter of God: if the world was created from the human mind, it is natural that the question arises as to where God can be seen there. The above-mentioned infinite being is God, the highest limit of striving for it is the human mind (the limited world of ideas).

As a philosopher, Mamardashvili mentions the existence and systematic nature of "real philosophy" and gives the following theories to philosophy: Basically, movement, recognizing what is, is a part of our life, our ability to determine what is happening and approach them.⁵⁵

We create a philosophy based on our approaches. Our world views are the place of a person in the world, his relation to this world, the system of general thoughts, affirmations, moods, and forgiveness of a person about the world. What is meant there is moment. Depending on how and when we live, our views on philosophy and the world are always changing. Basically, the same condition is imposed on science. (Science is abolished over time, new theories are created. In this case, the law of dialectics is used. Some features of the old theories are preserved, even if not completely, and are continued on the same basis. the following clause is correct: Philosophy helps us to understand our state after knowing what exactly our feelings express. It means thinking after thinking. After comparing the opinions of several people about philosophy, I came to this conclusion - I came to the opinion that his worldview is determined by his current forgiveness. Because the answers to the question, what is philosophy for you, were as follows - we can distinguish them according to age characteristics: 18-25 years old - for me, philosophy is wisdom, self-understanding, thoughts such as why I was born, how I can benefit others. 25-30 years old is a different dream for each person. For me, the aesthetic categories are sarcasm, humor and music. At the same time, some types of people are not very interested in philosophy.

CONCLUSIONS.

Now we will continue the theories given by Mamardashvili. Man's self-creating tool. According to Mamardashvili, man is a supernatural creation that cannot be reduced to natural forces, and cannot be described by the forces of nature. It

⁵⁵ М.К.Мамardashvili – Лекции о Прусте.

develops itself. Nature is the subject of human activity. About thinking - a person who has a desire to think, puts himself into action and forms himself anew. Doctrine of thinking: Mamardashvili derives from the uniqueness of being and thinking, since man is the thinking side, and being is the place where the thinker lives and moves, the differences between the two are not so great. This idea corresponds to the idea that Dakarttuń called "the existence of a being-thinking creation". Philosophy is a teaching about eternal problems (problems), and therefore the subject of philosophy itself is philosophy. Times change, theories and approaches change, old theories are replaced by new ones, and a new philosophy begins to be explained to a new person and the world.

REFERENCES:

1. A.Berdimurayova - *Filosofiya oqıw qollanbası*. (No'kis 2010)
2. M.Mamardashvili - *Эстетика мышления*. (M.2008)
3. Бийимбетов, Ж. (2016). Толерантлықтың социомәдений феномен сыпатында өзгешеликleri. вестник каракалпакского государственного университета имени бердаха, 31(2), 54-57.
4. Jaqsiliq, Biyimbetov. "Information Society Development Trends: Philosophical Analysis of Basic Concepts." *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies* 1.1 (2021): 74-77.
5. Kilishbaevich, B. J. (2022, December). Philosophical characteristics of information security and analysis of human problems in the 21st century. In *E Conference Zone* (pp. 1-3).
6. Kilishbaevich, Biyimbetov Jaksilik. "Problems of protection against threats affecting human consciousness in the processes of information civilization." *Conferencea* (2022): 1-3.
7. Biyimbetov, Jaksilik. "Philosophical analysis of the problem of information psychological security." *Адам әлемі* 88.2 (2021): 3-9.
8. Biyimbetov, J. K. "Political, economic, cultural and information development of the world in the process of globalization." *Science and education in Karakalpakstan. Karakalpak State University name after Berdakh-Нукыс* (2021): 91-92.
9. Biyimbetov, J. K. "Political, economic, cultural and information development of the world in the process of globalization." *Science and education in Karakalpakstan. Karakalpak State University name after Berdakh-Нукыс* (2021): 91-92.

10. Biyimbetov J. K. The problem of protecting people and society from information psychological threats //Military science development topical issues» international scientific and theoretical conference materials collection. Kazakstan.:– Almaty. – 2022. – С. 30-35.
11. Biyimbetov, J. K. (2022). Information wars as a socio-philosophical problem. Science and education in Karakalpakstan. Karakalpak State University name after Berdakh–Нукус, 281-283.
12. Biyimbetov, J. K. "Ismaylova GJ Insaniyattin jaña civilizaciyalıq rawajlanıwında informaciyalıq urıslardıń insan ruwxılıǵına tásirini." Global science and innovations (2020): 2-4.
13. Biyimbetov J. K. Philosophical and methodological analysis of the concepts of information and information society // Ўзбекистонда илмий-амалий тадқиқотлар» атамасидаги Республика. – С. 7-8.
14. Biyimbetov, J. K. "Jámiyettiń rawajlanıwında informaciyaǵa bolǵan talap hám informaciya mádeniyatı." Мир науки и духовной культуры в условиях глобализации и инновации (Сборник научных статей)» республика илмий-назарий конференцияси. Ўзбекистон.:–Нукус (2020): 175-177.
15. Biyimbetov J. K. Information security as an object of social philosophy //Science and education in Karakalpakstan. Karakalpak State University name after Berdakh–Нукус. – 2020. – С. 194-196.
16. Biyimbetov, J. K. (2020). Socio-philosophical analysis of the concept of information society. Science and education in Karakalpakstan. Karakalpak State University name after Berdakh–Нукус, 244-246.
17. BT, B. J. A., Joldasbaev, O. E., & Jamalov, N. Y. (2022). Insan turmısında mádeniyattin roli. Əжинияз номидаги Нукус давлат педагогика институтининг Фан ва жамият журналі.–Нукус: НДПИ, 50-51.
18. Kilishbayevich, Biyimbetov Jaksilik. "Philosophical analysis of manipulation and information security problems." Sustainability of education, socio-economic science theory 1.6 (2023): 143-146.
19. Biyimbetov, J. K. "Development of society in information and communication processes." Замоनावий фан, жамият ва таълим: долзарб масалалар, ютуқлар ва инновациялар 88 (2022).
20. Biyimbetov, J. K. "Қәуипсизликти тәмийнлеу мәселелериниң жәмийет турмысындағы әхмийети." Бердақ номидаги Қорақалпоқ давлат университетининг Ахборотномаси 174 (2020).

21. Biyimbetov, J. K. "Информация ҳам информациялык кәуипсизликтиң философиялык анализи." Бердак номидаги Қорақалпоқ давлат университетининг Ахборотномаси 83 (2019).
22. Biyimbetov, J. K. Information security of society as a current problem (based on experimental test results). Electronic journal of actual problems of modern science, education and training. Urganch. 83-87 (2023)
23. Perizat, Tlepbergenova. "Ecology of the Bukhara Deer in Our Country (Distribution and Origin)." *Research Journal of Applied Medical Sciences* 25 (2022).
24. Perizat, Tlepbergenova. "Global ecological problems: Essence and possible solutions." *International Journal of Academic Multidisciplinary Research (IJAMR)* (2021).
25. Tlepbergenova, P. "Ecology of education as part of the ecology of culture." *Uzbek scholar journal* (2022).
26. Tlepbergenova, P. "The modern problem of technogen pollution." *Materials of the republican*.
27. Perizat, Tlepbergenova. "Prospects For the Development of Ecological Tourism in Uzbekistan." *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies* (2021).
28. No'kisbaevna, Tlepbergenova Periyzat. "Prospects For the Development of Ecological Tourism in Uzbekistan." *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies* 2 (2021): 144-146.
29. Allamuratov, Maxmud, and Perizat Tlepbergenova. "Atmosfera's pollution as an actual global problem." *Innovative developments and research in education* 2.14 (2023): 42-48.
30. Allamuratov Maxmud, Tlepbergenova Perizat. "Problems of maintaining and ensuring environmental safety" Scientific approach to the modern education system. (2023): 101-105
31. Allamuratov Maxmud, Tlepbergenova Perizat. "The problem of technogen pollution to the environment". Science and education in Karakalpakstan. (2020): 17.